

Agrowaste derived phenolic compounds as additives to chitosan film for food packaging applications : Antibacterial and antioxidant study[†]

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Abstract : The objective of this study was to explore the incorporation and affect of agrowaste derived phenolic compounds (APCs) into chitosan films on their antibacterial and antioxidant behavior for food packaging. APCs were generated by treatment of agrowastes namely, rice husk, sugarcane baggasse and bamboo with dilute acid hydrolysis (0.5%, H₂SO₄) and isolated with the help of hydrophobic resin. The antibacterial activity of APCs loaded chitosan films was tested against microbial strains *B. subtilis* (Gram +ve) and *P. aeruginosa* (Gram -ve) bacteria. The results have shown significant inhibitory activity against these bacterial growths. The enhanced scavenging, reducing power and antioxidant activity of the films have been studied. The cytotoxicity of films was reduced by addition of APCs in other words polyphenolic compounds enhance the cell viability. The investigation has shown the benefits of incorporation of APCs into chitosan films and the potential for using waste materials as additives into chitosan based films for active food packaging applications.

Keywords : Agrowaste, phenolic compounds, chitosan, antibacterial, antioxidant, food packaging.

Introduction

The term agrowaste is used for one form of various kinds of biomasses which can be exploited for extracting useful chemical compound, while addressing the issue of disposal of potential wasteful materials. One of the major challenges of the food industry is the food preservation associated with active and time durable food packaging materials which are used universally for the protection and covering of food items¹. Presently, many ingredients are mixed and used for potential packaging to enhance antioxidant and antimicrobial property of food packaging systems². This is an indirect process to preserve the food quality and nutrient balance by continuous release of active ingredients or additives from packaging materials. With increasing health and economy concerns of the consumers, current researches are more focused on the use of cheap and cost effective natural additives in edible packaging materials^{3,4}. Further, there is increasing attention on the substitution of chemical additives with natural ones with a lower environmental shock and the use of natural antimicrobial and antioxidant compounds⁵. Agrowaste derived phenolic compounds (APCs) offer an alternative

in this regard. APCs having polyphenols, flavanols and tannins are well known to possess potential antioxidant activity with beneficial implications for human health⁶. Many types of phenolic compounds can be isolated while carrying out hydrolysis of agrowaste by dilute acid pre-treatment^{7,8}. The non-specificity of acid hydrolysis also leads to the formation of some by-products of sugar and lignin derivatives which are main inhibitory compounds in lignocellulosic bio-refineries along with fermentable sugars⁹. The lignin derivatived phenolics compounds includes vanillin, coumaric acid, syringic acid, ferulic acid, syringaldehyde, 4-hydroxybenzoic acid and benzaldehyde etc.^{11,12}. In food packaging materials phenolic compounds may prove to be major ingredients, with the only drawback that these compounds are not being able to remain active for longer periods. This problem may be overcome if these are mixed with a suitable film forming natural or biodegradable biopolymer such as chitosan. Lignin derived polyphenols and chitosan biopolymer composites have been focus of the attention of current researches¹³.

As such chitosan is a natural carbohydrate biopolymer of randomly distributed β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-N-acetyl-D-glucosamine

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

(deacetylated unit) and a fraction of β -(1 \rightarrow 4)-D-glucosamine (acetylated unit) and is derived by the deacetylation of chitin which is obtained from the shells of crustaceans. Chitosan can be fabricated into films, fibers, beads, nanomaterials and water soluble powder¹⁴. Its derivatives have high economic importance owing to their flexible biological activities such as biodegradability, biocompatibility, antimicrobial activity, and various other physicochemical properties¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Due to its antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, chitosan offers enormous opportunities for applications in antimicrobial food packaging^{18,19}. Although chitosan is a good biopolymer for active food packaging materials, it does not have significant antioxidant activity. Enhancement of antioxidant activity in chitosan can be a major challenge in boosting its applications in active food packaging materials⁶. Earlier studies have shown that antioxidant activity of chitosan, one of the chief functions for potential food packaging, could be enhanced through incorporating natural substances, such as green tea derived polyphenols extract¹⁹, green tea extract¹, Zataria multiflora Boiss essential oil, grape seed extract³, tea polyphenols (TP)^{4,6}, carvacrol and grape seed extract²⁰ and resveratrol²¹. Agrowastes which are rich source of huge quantity of phenolic compounds (APCs), with possible antioxidant properties have so far not been reported to be incorporated into chitosan films.

Thus, the present work is directed towards exploring the use of agrowastes (rice husk, sugarcane baggasse and bamboo) derived phenolic compounds (APCs) as potential additives for chitosan films and evaluating the properties of the resulting films in terms form of their structure along with antibacterial and antioxidant activity for food packaging applications.

Materials and methods :

Chemicals :

Chitosan (79% deacetylated, CIFT, Cochin), 3-(4,5-dimethyl-2-thiazolyl)-2,5-diphenyl-2H-tetrazolium bromide (MTT), DMSO, 1,1-diphenyl 2-picrylhyorazyl (DPPH SRL, India), acetone, glacial acetic acid, sulfuric acid and sodium hydroxide (CDH, India), catechol, organic solvent (isopropanol and ethanol) and Folin and Ciocalteu reagent (Merck, India), hydrophobic resin (XAD16, Sigma Aldrich, India, detail of physical and chemical parameters mentioned in manufacturer list), nutrient agar and

nutrient broth media (Himedia, India) were used. The test strains *Bacillus subtilis* (MTCC 121, Gram +ve) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC 1688, Gram -ve) were obtained from IMTECH, Chandigarh, India. Double distilled and Milli-Q grade water used throughout the experiment.

Agrowaste collection :

Agrowastes (sugarcane baggasse, rich husk and bamboo) were collected from local areas of Allahabad, India. Collected biomass were dried in oven (42 °C) for 3 days and cut into small pieces. Dried agrowaste was fractioned in gridding machine, broken into a particle dimension between average lengths of ~3-2 mm (with sieve) and again dried at 42 °C for overnight. Powered biomasses were kept in plastic seal pack bag until further utilization.

Treatment of agrowaste with acid :

Agrowaste derived phenolic compounds (APCs) obtained by acid hydrolysis with 10% (w/v) solid loading, 0.1% (v/v) H₂SO₄ at 121 °C for 1 h. Followed by high pressure autoclave (Mack Equipments Pvt. Ltd., India) technique. After that solid and liquid fractions were separated by muslin cloths, centrifuged and pH was adjusted to 5.0 by adding 1 N NaOH. The liquid fraction was stored in deep freeze for one week until further use and analysis.

Isolation of phenolic compounds :

Phenolic compounds in hydrolyzed liquid samples were isolated by a hydrophobic resin (XAD 16). The adsorptions of phenolic compounds were carried out with some modification by standard methods as described elsewhere²². Before the utilization of resin it was activated and washed with isopropanol and water (Milli-Q) for 30 min. XAD 16 was mixed (5%, w/v) with liquid samples (100 ml) in 250 ml flask at 30 °C and pH 2.0 with 120 rpm for 6 h in batch mode. After treatment, the adsorbed resin was separated and filtered from liquid fraction. Resin washed with Milli-Q water twice and filtered. The filtered resin was again treated with acetone and water (50 : 50) for desorption of phenolic compounds for 1 h from resin, and finally phenolic compounds and resin both were separated. Isolated phenolic compounds were freeze (8 °C) until further utilization and analysis.

Estimation of total phenolic compounds :

Total phenolic compounds content in the acid hydro-

lyzed agrowaste were estimated spectrophotometrically (Shimadzu UV spectrophotometer, USA) by modified Folin and Ciocalteu method²³. In brief, the reaction mixture of 0.1 ml test samples, 1.9 ml water and 0.5 ml Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1 N) was well shake and after 3 min, 2 ml of 10% Na₂CO₃ solution was added and mixed thoroughly. The reaction mixture was placed in a boiling water bath for exactly 3 min, cooled at room temperature in dark place and absorbance was measured at 650 nm.

Preparation of chitosan film :

Chitosan (CH) solution (2%, w/v in 0.5%, w/w aqueous solution of glacial acetic acid) at 30 °C with some modifications was prepared^{24,20}. APCs was added into chitosan solutions to reach a final concentration of 0.1 g/100 ml (w/v). All the solutions were kept for stirring, 2 h followed by sonication (Ultra sonic bath, Leela Electronics Pvt. Ltd., India) bath for 15 min, then filtered to obtain a clear solution. A casting method was used to obtain films in a dust free-environment and dried at 30 °C in air for 48 h. The dried films were carefully removed from the plates and stored for 48 h in desiccators at 25 °C before further tests. Prepared films are hereby named as CH (chitosan), SCB-CH (sugarcane bagasse and chitosan), BB-CH (bamboo and chitosan) and RH-CH (rice husk and chitosan).

Film thickness, solubility and water content :

Film thickness was determined with some modification by the method as described by Peng *et al.*¹. A digital micrometer with accuracy of 0.4 µm (Metra light, India) was used to measure the thickness of the films. Film thicknesses (micrometer) were measured on average of 10 random positions for each sample.

Water solubility of films was determined according to the method described by Rubilar *et al.*²⁰. Solubility is defined as the fraction of dry mass solubilized after 48 h immersion in water by using the equation as mentioned below :

$$\text{Solubility in water (\%)} = \frac{M_i - M_f}{M_i} \times 100$$

where M_i is the initial mass and M_f is the final mass (g) of the sample. Five replicates were taken for each sample.

For water content, films were weighed before and after dried in a hot oven at 80 °C for 48 h. Water content in films was calculated as follows :

$$\text{Water content (film)} = \frac{M_i - M_d}{M_i}$$

where M_i was the original film mass (g) and M_d was the dried film mass (g). Water content of film was presented as g H₂O/g wet base.

Antibacterial assessment :

For the investigation of antimicrobial activity of prepared film against two microbial strains of *B. subtilis* (Gram +ve) and *P. aeruginosa* (Gram -ve) were used. Antimicrobial test was performed by using agar disc diffusion method as described by Archana *et al.*²⁵. The incubation was continued for 24 h at 37 °C, and zone of inhibition around disc was measured to determine antibacterial efficacy.

Antioxidant assay :

DPPH radical scavenging assay :

Release test of antioxidant was based on the process described by Sun *et al.*²⁶ and Sharma *et al.*²⁷ with slight modification. The electron donating capability of the obtained APCs in film was measured by bleaching of the purple colored solution of DPPH radical. The absorbance was measured against a blank at 517 nm using spectrophotometer versus Milli-Q water as a blank with DPPH. All measurements were performed in triplicate. All data were taken as mean ± SD.

The DPPH radical scavenging activity (%) was calculated by the following : (blank-sample/blank) × 100, where blank is the absorption of the DPPH solution and sample is the absorption of the DPPH solution after the addition of the sample.

Phosphomolybdate assay (PMA) :

This is a spectroscopic method used for the quantitative determination of total antioxidant capacity through the formation of a phosphomolybdenum complex. The assay is based on the reduction of Mo^{VI} to Mo^V by the sample under analysis and subsequent formation of a green phosphate Mo^V complex at acidic pH. The total antioxidant capacity of the films and individual components (chitosan and phenolic compounds) were measured by the method described by Prieto *et al.*²⁸. The antioxidant activity was expressed as Vitamin C equivalent (mg of 100 g⁻¹ dry matter).

Reducing Power Assay (RPA) :

This method is based on the rule, that if there is an

increase in the absorbance of the reaction mixture, it will also increase the antioxidant activity. The reducing power assay for films and its constituents were determined by the method of Jaiprakash *et al.*²⁹. All the tests were performed in triplicate. A blank was prepared without adding standard or test compound. Increased absorbance of the reaction mixture indicated higher reducing power.

The antioxidant activity of the samples was compared with the standard ascorbic acid and gallic acid. The percent increase in reducing power was calculated using the following equation :

$$\text{Increase in reducing power (\%)} = \frac{A_{\text{test}} - A_{\text{blank}}}{A_{\text{blank}}} \times 100$$

where A test is absorbance of test solution; A blank is absorbance of blank.

Cell viability : MTT assay :

The quantitative estimation of cell viability/toxicity of films and polyphenols was done by calorimetric based MTT assay³⁰. A549 cell line (Human lung carcinoma, NCCS Pune) was maintained in Dulbecco's modified Eagles Medium (DMEM) complemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS). The cells 100 μL were seeded in 96-well tissue culture plates at the density of 1×10^5 cells/well in DMEM media supplemented with 10% FBS then incubated in CO₂ (5%) incubator with at 37 °C for 24 h. The cells were treated with different concentrations (0.05–1 mg/ml) of chitosan films and polyphenols respectively for 72 h at 37 °C. Then 20 μL of MTT (5 mg/ml prepared in 10 mM PBS buffer) solution was added in each well

and plate were incubated for another 4 h at 37 °C in dark. 200 μL dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was added into each well of the 96-well plate for 1 h and the solution was mixed to dissolve tetrazolium derived formazan precipitate. The absorbance was measured at 570 nm with microplate reader (BIO-RAD I Mark microplate reader, USA). Absorbance is directly proportional to the cell viability. The untreated cells were used as the control, and only media containing well has been taken as blank to calculate the percentage of cell viability in the treated samples. The percentage of cell viability was calculated by the formula : absorbance of sample – absorbance of blank/absorbance of control – absorbance of blank multiplied by 100.

Results and discussion

Preparation :

Agrowaste derived phenolic compounds (APCs) were obtained by acid hydrolysis methods and the detailed procedure is shown pictorially in Fig. 1.

Film thickness, solubility and water content :

The basic film properties, including thickness, water content and solubility in water are shown in Table 1. It has been observed that there are no major changes in the thickness of chitosan films after mixing of APCs. The water content of films decreased with the incorporation of APCs which has also been reported by Park and Zhao³¹ in similar studies. The decrease in the diffusivity of the water vapour through the matrix of the films has been attributed to the increase in the H-bonding interactions between phenolic compounds and chitosan³². Thus addi-

Fig. 1. Procedure applied for isolation of phenolic compounds from agrowaste.

tion of APCs in chitosan films results in the decrease in water solubility of the films. The percentage of water solubility of chitosan which was 29.12% without APCs, decreased to 16.52, 22.19 and 27.36% in the SCB-CH, BB-CH and RH-CH films respectively with 0.1 g containing APCs incorporation.

Table 1. Thickness, water content and solubility of APCs containing chitosan films

Films	Thickness (μm)	Water content (%)	Solubility in water (%)
Chitosan	136.5 \pm 0.8	17.25 \pm 0.3	29.12 \pm 0.7
SCB-CH	152.3 \pm 0.2	12.43 \pm 0.8	16.52 \pm 0.6
BB-CH	144.2 \pm 0.5	14.10 \pm 0.5	22.19 \pm 0.1
RH-CH	141.7 \pm 0.6	11.60 \pm 0.1	27.36 \pm 0.3

Antimicrobial activity :

It is clear that APCs alone as well as chitosan have potential antimicrobial activity. APCs themselves show a good antibacterial activity RH (11, 14 mm), SCB (19, 10 mm) and BB (8, 15 mm) but when it is mixed with chitosan; its activity got synergistically increased (Table 2). The films have shown large inhibiting zones against bacteria on the agar plate. These are found to be RH-CH (26, 29 mm), SCB-CH (33, 28 mm) and BB-CH (24, 3 mm). It is probably due to hydrophobic and lipophilic nature of phenolic compounds at the acidic pH²¹. The lipophilicity and steric effects of phenolic compounds may be two key factors in determining the overall inhibition of bacterial growth³³. It would be relevant to mention that polyphenolic compounds are well known for their bioactivity due to their capability to link/bond with proteins and bacterial membranes via complex formation through hydroxyl groups or phenolic rings³⁴.

Table 2. Inhibition zone (in mm) of APCs, chitosan and films against control

Films	Diameter (mm) of inhibitory zone against bacteria	
	<i>B. subtilis</i> (Gram +ve)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> (Gram -ve)
Control	8	2
CH	19	22
RH	11	14
SCB	19	10
BB	8	15
RH-CH	26	29
SCB-CH	33	28
BB-CH	24	32

Antioxidant activity :

Antioxidant activity of all chitosan-based films and their constituents were determined by three different methods : DPPH free radical scavenging assay, which assay the capacity of films to scavenge free radicals, phosphomolybdate assay (PMA) which evaluate total antioxidant capacity and Reducing Power Assay (RPA), which evaluates the iron reducing power of films. The free radicals scavenging activity of the films represented as RH-CH (81.7%), SCB-CH (94.3%) and BB-CH (84.8%) which is higher in compared to individual components of films. This activity can be recognized as the capacity of chitosan amino groups to react with free radicals (protonated ammonium NH_3^+) and free hydroxyl groups present in phenolic compounds help forming stable macromolecular radicals and groups³⁴. The reducing capacity of a compound serves as a significant indicator of its potential antioxidant activity. In the reduction of Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} by phenolic compounds, an electron is donated from the aromatic moiety which initiates the mechanism of phenolic antioxidant action. It has been also reported that there is a direct correlation between antioxidant activities and reducing power³⁵. The amount of reducing complex can then be monitored by measuring the formation of color product at 700 nm. Increasing absorbance exhibits increase in reducing power. Hence, reducing power of a compound serves as a significant indicator of antioxidants capacity, where regenerated inhibitory compounds are assayed for the reducing power activity. The absorbance of the prepared films in this study recorded at 700 nm has been found to increase incrementally in a dose dependent manner from 0.231 (23.1%) at 0.1 mg/ml to 0.988 (98.8%) at 1 mg/ml. For this assay ascorbic acid and gallic acid were used as a positive standard. The absorbance for standards ascorbic acid and gallic acid range from 0.137–0.602 (0.01–0.1 mg/ml) and 0.172–0.658 (0.1–1 mg/ml) respectively as shown graphically in Fig. 2.

The basic principle to assess the antioxidant capacity through phosphomolybdenum assay includes the reduction of Mo^{VI} to Mo^{V} by film and their constituents possessing antioxidant compounds. In the present study the antioxidant activity of APCs loaded chitosan films were found to be 2.60–6.39 mg/g of ascorbic acid equivalents. Though, APCs alone were more effective in reduction of Mo^{VI} to Mo^{V} . Antioxidant properties of phenolic com-

Fig. 2. Comparison of Reducing Power Assay (RPA) of films and their constituents with standard (gallic acid and ascorbic acid).

pounds are defined as compounds that can delay, inhibit, or stop the oxidation of oxidizable materials by scavenging free radicals and withdrawing oxidative stress. Recently, polyphenols have been considered as potent antioxidants *in vitro* and proved to be more potent antioxidants than Vitamin C and E and carotenoids^{21,36}. Besides the differences between the methodologies to conclude the antioxidant activity, all the chitosan based films incorporated with APCs showed higher antioxidant capacities than the respective constituents. The degree of antioxidant capacity of the films was generally proportional to the quantity of the antioxidant additives.

Cell viability : MTT assay :

The study of cell viability is a common assay for the evaluation of *in vitro* cytotoxicity of biomaterials. The MTT assay study was shown in Fig. 3 indicates that higher rate of cell death in case of chitosan itself whereas reduced toxicity was seen in case of APCs and its containing films. Cell viability decreased gradually increases the concentration of chitosan and also same type of results reported by others study³⁷. Polyphenolic compounds (APCs) improved the cell viability/life, through the reduction of cell oxidative stress, so that cell death was decreases³⁸.

Fig. 3. MTT assay of the APCs and prepared films.

Conclusions

The present study successfully demonstrates that an active antibacterial as well as antioxidant APCs impregnated chitosan films could be prepared by incorporating agrowaste derived phenolic compounds into chitosan film matrices. The mixing of phenolic compounds significantly improved the antioxidant and antibacterial activity of chitosan films. The addition of APCs in the prepared films also enhances the cell viability. Agrowastes (rice husk, sugarcane baggasse and bamboo) derived phenolic compounds (APCs) may thus be considered as useful additives to a natural biopolymer. The work highlights utilization of agrowaste in food packaging applications for storage, preservation and enhanced shelf life of food. The practicability of use of the newly synthesized chitosan based films is currently under progress in our laboratory.

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